

Comparison of Results for Delamination in Sandwich Hulls due to Local Water Slamming Loads using LSDYNA and Coupled FE-BEMs

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Abstract:

We study delamination in a sandwich hull due to transient finite plane strain elastic deformations caused by local water slamming loads and compare results obtained by using the commercial software, LSDYNA, and the in-house developed software based on the coupled finite element and boundary element methods (FE-BEMs). The cohesive zone model (CZM) is used to study delamination initiation and propagation. In analyzing water's deformations by the BEM, the water is assumed to be incompressible and inviscid, and its deformations irrotational. However, in LSDYNA, the fluid is taken to be compressible. Das and Batra have shown that the effect of water compressibility on the hydroelastic pressure induced by water slamming is negligible. Both approaches consider all geometric nonlinearities and take hull's material to be St. Venant–Kirchhoff. Results have been computed for deformable sandwich hulls with face sheets made of fiber reinforced composites and the core of soft materials. Strain energies of deformation in the core and the face sheets have been computed to determine which modes of deformation are dominant in the core and the face sheets. It is shown that the consideration of geometric nonlinearities significantly increases the peak hydrodynamic pressure and the delamination length. The delamination occurs in mode-II and it reduces the hydroelastic pressure acting on the hull surface and hence alters its deformations.

1 Introduction

Local water slamming is characterized by large hydrodynamic loads of short duration which can cause significant structural damage, e.g., see Faltinsen [1]. Review articles [2, 3] by Szebehely and Basin suggest that efforts should be

concentrated on non-linear free surface boundary conditions and the hydroelastic aspects of the impact. Here we focus on studying delamination mode of failure in sandwich hulls composed of stiff face sheets and a flexible core. A unique feature of the work is the consideration of both transverse normal and transverse shear deformations of face sheets and the core, all geometric nonlinearities, and assuming that the face sheets and the core are composed of St. Venant–Kirchhoff material. Thus a materially objective constitutive relation is employed.

Das and Batra [4] studied water slamming of deformable sandwich hulls using the commercial FE software LSDYNA with the arbitrary Lagrangian–Eulerian (ALE) formulation. They assumed the fluid to be compressible, accounted for inertia effects in the fluid and the solid, and examined delamination between the core and the face sheets. They pointed out that boundary conditions at the fluid/solid interface were not well satisfied since the fluid penetrated into the rigid hull. The pressure distribution on the wetted hull surface was found to be oscillatory, and the pre-post software swapped labels for the transverse shear and the transverse normal strains at a point of the sandwich hull. They studied delamination failure in a sandwich hull using the capability included in LSDYNA. Xiao and Batra [5] have studied finite transient deformations of a sandwich hull due to water slamming loads by using the coupled finite element and the boundary element methods (FE-BEMs). They assumed the fluid to be incompressible and its deformations to be irrotational. The same assumptions on fluid's deformations were made by Qin and Batra [6] who used a semi-analytical approach for delineating the hydroelastic pressure on the hull. Results reported in Refs. [4–6] suggest that the effect of water compressibility and its deformations being

irrotational are negligible on the hydrodynamic pressure acting on the hull. Whereas Qin and Batra [6] considered infinitesimal deformations of a sandwich hull, Xiao and Batra [5] accounted for all geometric nonlinearities. Furthermore, Qin and Batra used the first-order shear deformation theory for the face sheets and a third-order shear and normal deformation theory for the core. However, Xiao and Batra employed a third-order shear and normal deformable plate theory (TSNDT) for both the face sheets and the core.

Delamination is a common failure mode in sandwich structures because of low values of the interfacial strength. Methods employed to analyze delamination include linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) such as the virtual crack closure technique [7], the strain energy release rate (SERR) or the J-integral [8], the virtual crack extension [9], and the cohesive zone model (CZM) [10]. Critical ingredients of these methods are the delamination initiation and growth criteria. In the CZM surface tractions at a point on an interface are expressed as a non-monotonic function of the jump in displacements there with the area under the curve equalling the critical SERR. Zou et al. [11] proposed a damage surface by combining the conventional stress-based and fracture mechanics-based criteria for mixed-mode failures. Camanho and Dávila [12] described damage of the interface in terms of the mixed-mode relative displacement.

Here we compare results for delamination in a sandwich hull by using two approaches – the CZM coupled with the layer-wise third order shear and normal deformable plate/shell theory (TSNDT), and the CZM included in LSDYNA. As shown by Batra and Xiao [13] the TSNDT correctly predicts all components of surface tractions on interfaces between the core and the face sheets. The displacement field assumed for the TSNDT incorporates possible jumps in displacements at interfaces between the core and the face sheets. All geometric nonlinearities are considered in both approaches. The 2nd Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor is expressed as a linear function of the Green-St. Venant strain tensor. Thus a materially objective constitutive relation is employed. The initiation and propagation of delamination under mode-I, mode-II and mixed-mode deformations is studied.

2 Formulation of the Problem

A schematic sketch of the problem studied is shown in Fig. 1. At time $t = 0$, the ship hull keel impacts at

normal incidence with vertically downward velocity V stationary water occupying the semi-infinite domain $Z \leq 0$ when rectangular Cartesian coordinates (X, Y, Z) fixed to the earth are used to describe deformations of the fluid. We use material coordinates attached to the hull to identify its particles, and simplify the problem by assuming that the hull dimension in the Y -direction is much greater than that in the X - and Z -directions so that a plane strain state of deformation in the XZ -plane can be assumed and the problem can be solved as 2-dimensional (2-D). Furthermore, we assume that the hull geometry is symmetric about the plane $X = 0$ and it initially impacts water along the line $X = Z = 0$. Thus deformations of water in the region $X \geq 0$ and $Z \leq 0$ and of the right-half of the hull are analyzed.

We note that the hydrodynamic load which accounts for hull's deformations is highly localized; thus the slamming problem is idealized as that of a deformable sandwich wedge entering water with a uniform vertically downward velocity (see Fig. 1). We derive equations governing finite deformations of the hull and the water from balance laws of mass, linear momentum and moment of momentum, the strain-displacement relations appropriate for finite deformations, and constitutive relations. Additional nonlinearities are the *a priori* unknown length of the wetted surface which is a nonlinear function of hull's deformations, and the deformed shape of the free surface of water. Of course, the shape of the free surface of water is to be determined as a part of the solution of the problem.

For hull speeds of the order of 10 m/s, viscous effects in water are often neglected. Also, as shown by Das and Batra [4] the compressibility of water plays a negligible role. We thus assume water to be incompressible, and its deformations to be irrotational.

Thus there exists a velocity potential φ such that velocity $\mathbf{v} = -\nabla\varphi$, where ∇ is the spatial gradient operator in the XZ -plane. The assumption of incompressibility requires that φ satisfy the Laplace equation. We refer the reader to Ref. [5] for a detailed description of governing equations, and initial and boundary conditions. We note that deformations of the hull and the fluid are coupled since hull's deformations are affected by the pressure exerted on it by the fluid and fluid's by constraining the velocity field of water touching the hull to be along its surface. Recall that the

Fig. 1 Schematic sketch of the water slamming problem studied.

tangential velocity of the contacting fluid and hull particles can be discontinuous since water is assumed to inviscid.

For 2-D problems being studied here, we model the hull as a sandwich beam having three (for simplicity) layers and denote displacements of a point in the top, the central, and the bottom layers by superscripts t, c and b, respectively. With the origin of the coordinate axes located at the geometric centroid of the hull cross-section we assume the following displacement field in the beam.

$$u_{\alpha}^c(y_1, y_3, t) = \sum_{i=0}^3 (y_3)^i u_{\alpha i}^c(y_1, t), \quad (1.a)$$

$$\alpha = 1, 3, \quad |y_3| \leq h^c$$

$$u_{\alpha}^t(y_1, y_3, t) = u_{\alpha}^c(y_1, h^c, t) + u_{\alpha 0}^t + \sum_{i=1}^3 \left((y_3)^i - (h^c)^i \right) u_{\alpha i}^t(y_1, t), \quad (1.b)$$

$$\alpha = 1, 3, \quad h^c \leq y_3 \leq h^c + h^t$$

$$u_{\alpha}^b(y_1, y_3, t) = u_{\alpha}^c(y_1, -h^c, t) - u_{\alpha 0}^b + \sum_{i=1}^3 \left((y_3)^i - (-h^c)^i \right) u_{\alpha i}^b(y_1, t), \quad (1.c)$$

$$\alpha = 1, 3, \quad -(h^b + h^c) \leq y_3 \leq -h^c$$

Here u_{10}^c and u_{30}^c are, respectively, the axial and the transverse displacements of a point on the beam mid-surface, $u_{\alpha i}^c, u_{\alpha i}^t$ and $u_{\alpha i}^b$ ($\alpha = 1, 3, i = 1, 2, 3$) are generalized axial and transverse displacements of a point, and $u_{\alpha 0}^c$ and $u_{\alpha 0}^b$ ($\alpha = 1, 3$) represent jumps in displacements between adjoining points on the top and the bottom interfaces, respectively.

Nonzero values of $u_{\alpha 0}^t$ and $u_{\alpha 0}^b$ at a point imply that the two layers have either started to delaminate or have delaminated there. The top (bottom) interface is between the core and the top (bottom) face sheet. The jumps δ_n and δ_t in the normal and tangential displacements at a point on the interface between the top layer and the core appearing in the CZM relation are related to the displacement field $u_{\alpha}(y_1, y_3, t)$ by using the transformation rules for vectors. We refer

the reader to [14] for derivation of the governing equations, boundary conditions for the TSNDT, and a weak formulation of the initial-boundary-value problem (IBVP)

We assume that the normal (tangential) tractions at a point on the interface between the core and a face sheet is related to the jump in the corresponding normal (tangential) displacement by a polynomial of degree one, and refer the reader to [5] for details.

3 Results

3.1 Numerical Solution of the Problem

We use the BEM to analyze deformations of the fluid by truncating its domain to a finite size which is determined iteratively till the hydrodynamic pressure acting on the hull is unaffected by the size of the fluid domain. During the solution of the problem, the thickness of the water layer between the free surface and the hull near the terminus of the wetted length of the hull becomes very small. It necessitates reducing the time step size for analyzing subsequent deformations of the fluid and the hull. As explained in [15] for a rigid hull, we cut the thin jet, smoothen the free surface, re-mesh it and derive values of variables at the newly generated nodes by interpolating and extrapolating from those at nodes of the previous mesh.

We introduce the stiffness proportional Rayleigh damping to reduce high frequency vibrations of the hull, and solve for hull's deformations by using the FEM.

The verification of the FE software for analyzing hull's deformations is described in [13] and the verification of the software for delamination analysis is discussed in [14]. The developed BEM software has been verified in [15] by using the method of manufactured solutions (e.g., see the material just preceding and following Eq. 20 of [16]). The

coupling between the FE and the BE software is verified by analyzing problems for rigid hulls and comparing computed results with those available in the literature, e.g., see [15].

3.2 Water slamming of linear elastic straight sandwich hull

In order to verify our approach and the software, we first analyze deformations of a clamped-clamped linear elastic straight sandwich hull of length $\mathcal{L} = 1$ m, thickness of each face sheet $h^b = h^t = 1.2$ cm, core thickness $2h^c = 3.0$ cm, and downward impact velocity = 10 m/s. Effects of gravity have been neglected. Values of material parameters are listed in Table 1. The mass density assigned to face sheets includes the dead weight of the ship. The sandwich beam is divided into 60 uniform 2-node elements along the y_1 -axis, and the fluid domain is truncated to have L_1 and L_2 equal to 15 m. As shown in [5] through numerical experiments these values of L_1 and L_2 give converged results. The FE and the BE meshes are successively refined till the computed solution has converged within the prescribed tolerance. The time steps used to compute results equaled 0.19, 0.37, and 0.53 μ s for deadrise angle, $\beta = 5^\circ, 10^\circ,$ and 14° , respectively

For the hull of initial deadrise angle 5° we set the Rayleigh damping coefficient $\alpha = 5 \times 10^{-6}$. In Fig. 2 the presently computed time histories of the deflection of the hull centroid for three different values of the initial deadrise angle are compared with those found by Das and Batra [4] who used LSDYNA and by Qin and Batra [6] who employed a semi-analytical approach. Solutions from the three methods are close to each other for initial deadrise angles of 5° and 10° , but differences among them are large for initial deadrise angle of 14° . We note that Qin and Batra [6] assumed small values of the

Table 1 Values of material parameters of the sandwich hull

	C_{1111} (GPa)	C_{1133} (GPa)	C_{3333} (GPa)	C_{1313} (GPa)	Mass density (kg/m ³)
Face sheet	140.3	3.77	9.62	7.10	31,400
Core	3.77	1.62	3.77	1.08	150

Fig. 2 For initial impact speed = 10 m/s, time histories of the hull centroid deflection for initial deadrise angle = 5°, 10° and 14°. Black, blue and red curves represent results from Qin and Batra [6], Das and Batra [4], and the present work, respectively.

Fig. 3 At $t = 5.471$ ms after impact, deformed shapes of the mid-surface of the hull computed by the three methods.

initial deadrise angle of the hull. The deformed shapes at $t = 5.47$ ms of the mid-surface of the hull of initial deadrise angle = 5° computed by the three methods plotted in Fig. 3 are close to each other, with percentage difference, $100 \int_0^L |u_3 - u_3^{pre}| ds / \int_0^L |u_3^{pre}| ds$, equal to 10 % and 6.2 %, respectively, for solutions of u_3 given in [6] and [4]. Here, u_3^{pre} is the value of u_3 computed by using the coupled FE-BEMs.

Fig. 4 exhibits time histories of the slamming pressure at locations $y_1 = 0.24, 0.35$ and 0.57 m of the hull of initial deadrise angle = 5°. The peak pressure predicted by the present method is very high and qualitatively resembles that given by Qin and Batra's [6] semi-analytical approach, and it is much higher than that found in [4] using LSDYNA.

Fig. 4 Time histories of the pressure at three locations of the hull of initial deadrise angle 5°; black, blue and red curves represent results from Qin and Batra [6], Das and Batra [4], and the present method, respectively.

Table 2 Comparison of LSDYNA and coupled BE-FE approaches for the water slamming problem

	LSDYNA	BE-FE methods
Fluid penetrates into solid	Yes	No
Oscillations in pressure on the hull	Yes	No
Results depend on contact algorithm	Yes	No
Computation of water jet	Difficult	Easy
Assumptions for fluid deformations	Compressible and no restrictions on fluid's deformations	Incompressible and irrotational
Evaluation of deformations at a point in the fluid domain	Easy	Difficult
Information for nodes on cohesive elements	Needed	Not needed

We note that in the modified Wagner’s theory employed in [6] the pressure field is singular and its peak value is approximated. Except for the peak pressure, the three methods give results that are close to each other.

We have listed in Table 2 salient features of solutions of the water slamming problem using the FE software LSDYNA and the present coupled BE-FE approach.

3.3 Water slamming of straight sandwich hull made of St. Venant-Kirchhoff material

Two water slamming problems have been simulated to delineate the influence on the hydrodynamic pressure acting on a sandwich hull of geometric nonlinearities and hull stiffness. For problem 1 values of elastic constants are the same as those for the hull studied in subsection 3.1, and for problem 2, values of all elastic parameters have been reduced by a factor of 10 and the mass density reduced to 2,000 kg/m³. For problem 2 we set $h^t = h^b = 6$ mm, $h^c = 7.5$ mm, and $\mathcal{L} = 1$ m. The deadrise angle and the downward velocity of the hull for both problems equal 10° and 10 m/s, respectively. Effects of geometric nonlinearities are considered only for problem 2. The time steps used to compute results equaled 0.75 μs for both problems.

Time histories of the hull centroid deflection are plotted in Fig. 5. For problem 2, the maximum percentage difference $100|w_{lin} - w_{non}|/w_{lin}$ between the hull centroid deflections with (w_{non}) and without (w_{lin}) considering geometric nonlinearities is 32.5%. The time histories of centroidal deflections for the two linear problems suggest that the hull of problem 1 is considerably stiffer than that of problem 2. From results for the two linear problems we deduce that the peak pressure on the stiffer hull that deflects less is nearly 80% more than that on the flexible hull. At a fixed value of time the wetted length is larger for the stiffer hull than that for the flexible hull.

Fig. 6 exhibits time histories of the hydrodynamic pressure on the hull at three different locations with arc length in the deformed shape equal to 0.24, 0.35, and 0.57 m. These results suggest that the consideration of geometric nonlinearities significantly increases the maximum hydroelastic pressure acting on the hull. For example, at $x = 0.57$ m, the peak hydroelastic pressures at $t \approx 9$ ms for the nonlinear problem equals 1.4 times that for the linear problem. It could be due to the fact that

the stiffness of the hull considering geometrically nonlinear deformations is more than that of the identical hull for which geometric nonlinearities are not considered. At $x = 0.57$ m, the peak hydrostatic pressure occurs sooner for the nonlinear problem than that for the linear problem. The traveling wave like behavior of the hydroelastic pressure is unaffected by the consideration of geometric nonlinearities.

3.4 Delamination in linear elastic straight sandwich hull due to water slamming loads

We now analyze two problems involving delamination initiation and growth in a clamped-clamped linear elastic straight sandwich hull of length $\mathcal{L} = 1$ m. The hull is divided into 81 uniform 2-node elements along the y_I -axis. For problem 1, the geometric and material parameters, and the entry velocity are the same as those for the hull studied in subsection 3.2 and the deadrise angle $\beta = 5^\circ$. We

Fig. 5 Time histories of the hull centroid deflection

Fig. 6 Time histories of the hydroelastic pressure on the hull at three points with arc length in the deformed shape equal to 0.24 m, 0.35 m and 0.57 m. Black, red and blue curves represent results for linear problem 1, linear problem 2 and nonlinear problem 2, respectively.

assume that the interface strength parameters have values $\sigma_t^0 = \sigma_n^0 = 1 \text{ MPa}$, $G_{Ic} = 625 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$, $G_{IIc} = 418 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$. Delamination in the hull of problem 1 has been studied by Das and Batra [4] using LSDYNA and the above listed values of parameters. For problem 2, we assume that the thickness of each face sheet, $h^b = h^t = 2 \text{ cm}$, core thickness, $2h^c = 6.0 \text{ cm}$, downward impact velocity = 10 m/s and deadrise angle $\beta = 10^\circ$. The face sheets and the core are assumed to be made of GRP and PVC foam (H200), respectively, and the interface parameters have values, $\sigma_t^0 = 3.5 \text{ MPa}$, $\sigma_n^0 = 7.1 \text{ MPa}$, $G_{Ic} = 625 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$, $G_{IIc} = 418 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$. The material properties for the face sheets and the experimental value of the critical interface SERR for mode II delamination are taken from [17]. Values of the critical interface SERR for mode I delamination and the mass density of the GRP are not provided in [17], and these have been taken from [18] and [19], respectively. Values of material parameters, listed in Table 3, for the core and the interface strength are taken from [20]. The time steps used to compute results for problems 1 and 2 equaled $0.19 \mu\text{s}$ and $0.75 \mu\text{s}$, respectively.

For problem 1, we compare the presently computed results with those of [4] obtained by using LSDYNA and the stress criterion to predict the delamination and failure of the interface. When using the stress criterion the failure occurs instantaneously when the criterion is satisfied. Fig. 7 exhibits time histories of the deflection of the hull centroid with and without considering delamination. It is clear that the presently computed results are close to those of [4], and the hull centroid deflection considering delamination is larger than that without accounting for delamination. The sandwich hull's stiffness decreases subsequent to the onset of delamination.

The variations of the hydroelastic pressure on the hull surface for two values of time are shown in Fig. 8. We note that the hydroelastic pressure on a delaminated hull is less than that on the

corresponding in-tact hull because the hull stiffness is reduced due to delamination.

In order to determine from where and when delamination initiates first, we define the separation index, ω , by

$$\omega = \sqrt{\left(\frac{G_I}{G_{Ic}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIc}}\right)^2} \quad (2)$$

where G_I and G_{II} are the strain energy release rates for mode I and mode II deformations respectively. It equals 1 at a point when complete delamination has occurred there. In Fig. 9, we have plotted the variation of ω versus time t and y_1 -coordinate on the two interfaces for problem 2. We note that ω equals the square root of the left hand side of Eq. (2), $G_I = \int \sigma_n d\delta_n$ and $G_{II} = \int \sigma_t d\delta_t$ and have taken the hull width (dimension in the y_2 -direction) equal to 1 m. It is clear that the complete delamination first occurs on both interfaces at points close to the left edge or near $y_1 = 0$ at about $t = 6.5 \text{ ms}$, and propagates to the right edge of the beam on both interfaces.

The two interfaces are delaminated at different rates with the top and the bottom interfaces completely delaminated at approximately $t = 9.1$ and 10.5 ms , respectively. The delamination process is unstable as evidenced by the sharp increase followed by arrest in the delamination lengths. Also, at $t = 9 \text{ ms}$, a large portion of both interfaces near the right edge is delaminated very rapidly.

Time histories of the strain energy W_e and the kinetic energy W_k of the hull, the external work W_p done by the water slamming pressure and of the energy W_d dissipated during delamination are exhibited in Fig. 10. The energies W_e and W_k are evaluated by integrating over the hull domain the elastic energy density W and the kinetic energy density, respectively. The work W_p of water

Table 3 Values of material parameters of the sandwich hull

	C_{1111} (GPa)	C_{1133} (GPa)	C_{3333} (GPa)	C_{1313} (GPa)	Mass density (kg/m ³)
Face sheet	13.4	2.40	5.92	1.92	1,850
Core	0.307	1.62	0.0923	0.107	200

Fig. 7 Time histories of the deflection of the straight hull centroid with and without considering delamination

Fig. 8 Distribution of the hydroelastic pressure on the hull at two different times. Black and red curves represent results with and without considering delamination, respectively. The red and black curves at $t = 2.72$ ms for problem 2 overlap as the beam has not been delaminated at this time.

Fig. 9 Variation of the separation index ω with y_1 -coordinate and time, on the top and the bottom interfaces for problem 2.

Fig. 10 Time histories of the work done by external forces, strain energy stored in the hull, kinetic energy and energy dissipated during delamination.

slamming pressure equals $\iint (p - p_a) H_1 d\Delta dy_1$, and the energy W_d of delamination equals $\int_{\Gamma_c} (G_{Ic} + G_{IIc}) H_1 dy_1$. Here Δ is the normal deflection of the hull, and Γ_c are the two cohesive interfaces between face sheets and the core. The energy dissipated during the delamination process is a miniscule part of the total work done by external forces. Discontinuities in the time histories of the elastic strain energy at about $t = 6.5$ and 9 ms are due to the unstable growth of delamination.

5 Conclusions

Delamination in deformable straight sandwich hulls due to water slamming loads has been studied using coupled boundary and finite element methods, and results have been compared with those computed using the commercial software, LSDYNA. It is found that the two approaches give very close results suggesting thereby that the assumptions of water being incompressible and its deformations being irrotational do not noticeably influence the hydroelastic effects. The consideration of geometric nonlinearities significantly increases the maximum hydrodynamic pressure experienced by the hull. However, it does not affect the traveling wave like behavior of the hydroelastic pressure acting on the hull. For the problem studied, the delamination occurred at the two interfaces between the core and the face sheets due to mode-II deformations.

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